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4 **Effect of Temperature, Wetness Duration, and Planting Density on Olive**
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6 **Anthracnose Caused by *Colletotrichum* spp.**
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28
29 **ABSTRACT**
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34 temperature, wetness duration, and planting density on olive anthracnose caused by
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36 *Colletotrichum* spp. *Phytopathology* 101: XXX-XXX
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40 The influence of temperature, wetness duration, and planting density on infection of
41
42 olive fruit by *Colletotrichum acutatum* and *C. simmondsii* was examined in laboratory
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44 and field experiments. Detached olive fruit of cvs. Arbequina, Hojiblanca, and Picual
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46 were inoculated with conidia of several isolates of the pathogen and kept at constant
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48 temperatures ranging from 5 to 35°C in humid chambers. Similarly, fruit, potted plants,
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50 and stem cuttings with fruit were inoculated and subjected to wetness periods ranging
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52 from 0 to 48 h. Infection occurred from 10 to 25°C, and disease severity was greater and
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54 the mean latent time was shorter between 17 and 20°C. Overall, *C. acutatum* was more
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56 virulent than *C. simmondsii* at temperatures <25°C. When temperature was not a
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3 limiting factor, disease severity increased with the wetness period from 0 to 48 h.
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5 Disease severity was modeled as a function of both temperature and wetness duration
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7 using Magarey's model; two critical fruit incidence thresholds were defined as 10 and
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9 20%, with wetness durations of 2.6 and 12.2 h at the optimum temperature. In the field,
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11 anthracnose epidemics progressed faster in a superhigh-density planting (1904 olive
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13 trees/ha) than in the high-density plantings (from 204 to 816 olive tree/ha) and caused
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15 severe epidemics in the superhigh-density planting even with the moderately resistant
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17 cv. Arbequina. The data in this study will be useful for the development of a forecasting
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19 system for olive anthracnose epidemics.
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26 Anthracnose is the most important disease of olive (*Olea europaea*) fruit and is
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28 widespread in many olive-growing regions of the world, including southern Spain (21).
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30 Olive anthracnose is caused by two species of *Colletotrichum*, *Colletotrichum acutatum*
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32 J.H. Simmonds and *C. gloeosporioides* (Penz.) Penz. & Sacc., (16,29). In Portugal and
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34 Spain, *C. acutatum* is the dominant species and *C. gloeosporioides* occurs only
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36 infrequently. (16,23,29). Subsequent to the research cited previously in this paragraph,
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38 *C. acutatum* was reclassified as *C. simmondsii*, *C. fioriniae*, and *C. acutatum* s.s. (26).
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40 The teleomorphs of *C. acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* are known but have never been
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42 observed in olive orchards in southern Spain.
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47 The pathogen mainly attacks olive fruit, causing a typical rot called "soapy fruit"
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49 (7,20). In Spain, the fungus produces toxins in the rotten fruit that cause leaf wilting and
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51 branch dieback several weeks after plants exhibit soapy fruit symptoms (21). In years
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53 when the disease is severe, anthracnose reduces yields by an average of 6% in Spain (7)
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55 and by up to 50% in other countries (4,11,28,29,31). Field observations in southern
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57 Spain indicated that the disease is particularly severe in orchards that are densely
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3 planted with susceptible olive cultivars, although the effect of plant density has not been
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5 studied (31).
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8 Although much research has been conducted on olive anthracnose (16,20,21,29),
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10 little information exists on the effects of environment on disease epidemics. In addition
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12 to temperature and fruit maturity, rainfall is probably a critical factor in most olive
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14 anthracnose epidemics (19,20,28). Most of this research has been done in the field, and
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16 information on the precise effects of environmental variables on olive anthracnose
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18 under controlled conditions is scarce (11,19,20,28). This information is required for
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20 understanding and controlling many foliar pathogens, and is essential for the
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22 development of an infection sub-model, which is a critical component in disease
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24 forecasting (14). For most fungal pathogens in most terrestrial environments, infection
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26 is usually limited by the duration of surface wetness or high humidity and temperature
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30 (5).
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33 High production costs, especially for harvest, have resulted in the redesign of olive
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35 orchards during the last 30 years. Traditional olive orchards in Spain had a relatively
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37 low density of trees (70–80 trees/ha). Modern olive oil producers are planting trees at
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39 200-400 trees/ha in high-density systems and at 2000 trees/ha in superhigh-density
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41 systems in which the trees form hedgerows (2,24). These increased tree densities may
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43 favor the development of epidemics of airborne pathogens by increasing the duration of
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45 wetness on the leaves and fruit.
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48 Knowledge of environmental and agronomic influences on disease development is
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50 important for the proper timing of fungicide applications for control of olive
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52 anthracnose. Precise information could aid in developing models that predict the
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54 development of epidemics during the autumn. Thus, the objectives of this work were to
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56 determine the influence of temperature and wetness duration on fruit on infection by
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Colletotrichum species and to determine the effect of tree density on the incidence of affected fruit.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fruit, potted plants, and stem cuttings. Three commercial olive cultivars with different degrees of resistance to anthracnose (18) were used: Hojiblanca (susceptible), Arbequina (moderately susceptible), and Picual (resistant). Olive fruit were collected from healthy field-grown trees in the provinces of Córdoba and Jaén (Andalusian region, southern Spain). Depending on the experiment and trial within experiment (these are described later in the Methods), the fruit used were green, green-yellow, or black with values of 0, 1, or 4, respectively, according to the 0-to-4 ripening index (25). Olive fruit were washed in tap water, surface sterilized in a 10% solution of commercial bleach (50 g of Cl/liter) for 1 min, rinsed with sterile water, and air-dried on a laboratory bench. Disinfested fruit were placed in plastic containers and stored at 4°C until used (within 7 days). Disinfested fruit were preconditioned at room temperature ($23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) for 4 to 6 h before inoculation with isolates of *Colletotrichum* (20). In the wetness-duration experiment (experiment 2), 4-year-old potted olive plants of cv. Hojiblanca and 2-year-old plants of cv. Arbequina from a commercial nursery were used in trial 1 and 2, respectively. The age difference between the cultivars was due to the shorter non-productive period for cv. Arbequina than cv. Hojiblanca (2). Plants were grown in natural soil in 7-liter plastic containers until they were used in experiments. Plants were fertilized once (7 g of P_2O_5 + 2 g of KNO_3 + 1 g of CaCO_3 + 1 g of MgSO_4 + 0.6 g of MgCO_3 per plant) and irrigated as needed. In trial 3 of the wetness-duration experiment, 30- to 40-cm pieces of stem with 5–15 olive fruit were cut from healthy field-grown trees of cv. Arbequina in Córdoba. The stems were planted in moist,

sterilized perlite in plastic boxes (60 × 40 × 20 cm) to prevent dehydration of fruit before inoculation.

Isolates. Isolates Col-09, Col-30, Col-87, and Col-104 were obtained from fruit on diseased olive trees from different orchards in the Andalusian region. The selected isolates represented the range of morphological characteristics typical of olive anthracnose pathogens. Isolates Col-09 and Col-30 had morphological characteristics similar to those of *C. acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* morphospecies, respectively. Isolates Col-87 and Col-104, in contrast, exhibited morphological and physiological characteristics intermediate between both species (23). All isolates were identified as *C. acutatum*-group A4 according to their internal transcribed spacer 5.8S and β -tubulin regions (29); *C. acutatum*-group A4 is the dominant group in central Andalusia (J. Moral and A. Trapero, *unpublished data*). The Italian isolate Col-116 (Monte Falco, Perugia region, Italy) was also used in some experiments. Based on molecular data, this isolate was identified as *C. acutatum*-group A2, which is prevalent in Portugal (29), but *C. acutatum*-group A2 was subsequently reclassified as *C. simmondsii* (26). Single-spore isolates were cultured in petri dishes containing potato dextrose agar (PDA) (Difco Laboratories, Detroit, MI) acidified with lactic acid (25% [vol/vol] at 2.5 ml/liter of medium). Petri dishes were incubated at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with a 12-h photoperiod of fluorescent light ($350 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) for 1 week. To ensure that the conidia used were viable, we measured the germination of each batch of inoculum before inoculation. The density of conidia in the inoculum was measured with a hemacytometer and was then diluted to 10^5 conidia/ml.

Inoculation and incubation. Detached fruit and plants were sprayed to incipient runoff with the conidial suspension using an electric sprayer (Black & Decker® 58-

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102). Non-inoculated controls for detached fruit or plants were sprayed with distilled water plus Tween® 20.

Incubation treatments differed among experiments. Detached olives (experiment 1) were maintained in humid (100% RH) plastic containers ($22 \times 16 \times 10 \text{ cm}^3$) that were placed in growth chambers at different temperatures in the dark until the end of experiment. In general, plants and stem cuttings (experiment 2) were incubated during the “wetness period” in moist chambers that consisted of closed, dark-plastic cages containing plastic pans filled with water to provide 100% relative humidity (RH). After the wetness period, inoculated plants and stem cuttings were dried at room temperature ($22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). The stem cuttings were then transferred to a growth chamber at 20°C for 4 days in the dark and then in fluorescent light with a 14-h photoperiod and 50 to 90% RH. Unlike the stem cuttings, the plants were transferred to the greenhouse at $15\text{--}30^\circ\text{C}$ and $\text{RH} < 70\%$ after the wetness period.

Effect of temperature on infection (experiment 1). *Trial 1.* Ripe, black fruit (ripening index value of 4) of cv. Hojiblanca were inoculated with isolates Col-09 and Col-30 and kept in humid chambers. The humid chambers were placed in darkened growth chambers at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, and 35°C . A disease severity index (DSI) was recorded at 7, 10, and 14 days after inoculation. DSI was calculated for each replication with the following formula: $\text{DSI} = (\sum ni \times i) / N$, where i represents severity (0 to 5), ni is the number of fruit with the severity of i , and N is the total number of fruit (20). There were three replicate humid chambers (25 fruit per chamber) for each combination of isolate and temperature.

Trial 2. Green-yellow fruit (ripening index value of 1) of cvs. Hojiblanca and Picual were inoculated with isolates Col-104 and Col-116 and placed in humid chambers as described above. The DSI was recorded periodically for 6 weeks. For each

temperature, DSI values were regressed against time with the formula: $DSI = b \times t$, where t = time in days and b = symptom development rate (day^{-1}). For each temperature, a mean latent period (MLP) was calculated with the following formula:

$$MLP = \frac{\sum \Delta I_i \times t_i}{I_{\max}}$$

where ΔI_i is the increase in the percentage of symptomatic fruit at each interval, $G_{i+1} - G_i$, t_i is the average number of days for each time interval $[(t_{i+1} + t_i)/2]$, and I_{\max} is the percentage of symptomatic fruit for each temperature at the maximum incubation period (6 weeks). Each combination of isolate and temperature was represented by three replicate humid chambers.

Trial 3. This trial was identical to trial 2 except that the inoculated fruit were pre-incubated at the optimum temperature (20°C) for 48 h to ensure infection before they were incubated at final temperatures of 5 to 35°C as described above.

Effect of wetness duration on infection (experiment 2). *Trial 1.* Four-year-old olive plants of cv. Hojiblanca with green fruit (ripening index value of 0) were inoculated with isolate Col-87 as described above during September. The plants were placed in moist chambers in darkened growth chambers at 20°C. Plants were subjected to 0-, 6-, 12-, 24, or 48-h wetness periods. At the end of the wetness period, plants were removed from the moisture chambers, dried for 30 min, and then moved to the greenhouse as described above. Additionally, three inoculated plants were dried immediately after inoculation at 22°C for 48 h and transferred to moist chambers for 48 h before they were transferred to the greenhouse to serve as a 48/48-h wetness period treatment. DSI was recorded for 4 months. For each wetness period and replication, the standardized area under the disease progress curve (SAUDPC) was calculated by trapezoidal integration of DSI values over time expressed as a percentage of a

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3 maximum theoretical curve. Three replicate plants were subjected to each wetness
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5 period.
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8 *Trial 2.* Two-year-old plants of cv. Arbequina with green-yellow fruit (value 1 in
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10 the ripening index) were inoculated in November with isolate Col-87. Plants were
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12 subjected to 0-, 1.5-, 3-, 6-, 12-, 24-, or 48-h wetness periods and incubated as described
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14 above. Fruit were collected 6 weeks after inoculation because most did not show any
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16 anthracnose symptoms. The percentage of fruit with latent infections of *C. acutatum*
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18 was determined using the herbicide N,N'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium dichloride
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20 (Paraquat). For each sample, fruit were washed with sterile-distilled water for 30 min,
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22 surface disinfested by successive immersion in 70% ethanol for 2 min and in a 20%
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24 solution of commercial bleach (50 g of Cl/liter) in sterile water for 7 min, rinsed with
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26 sterile water, and dipped in Paraquat (Paratex, 200 g/liter; Aragonesas Agro S.A.,
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28 Madrid, Spain) at 2.9 g/liter of water for 1 min (21). The herbicide killed the fruit cells
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30 and thereby permitted rapid colonization by latent fungal propagules. Five replicate
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32 plants were subjected to each wetness period.
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37 *Trial 3.* Because the fruit from non-inoculated (control) potted plants in trial 2 of
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39 this experiment showed latent infection by the pathogen, the trial was repeated using
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41 stem cuttings of cv. Arbequina with green-yellow fruit. The same isolates and wetness
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43 duration treatments were used. The inoculated stem cuttings were incubated at $23 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$
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45 and 50 to 90% RH with a 12-h photoperiod of fluorescent light ($350 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) for 2
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47 weeks. Paraquat was used again to evaluate the percentage of affected fruit. Five
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49 replicate stem cuttings were subjected to each wetness period.
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52 **Effect of planting density on incidence of affected fruit (experiment 3).**

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54 Experiment 3 was conducted in a research orchard of cv. Arbequina located in Córdoba
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56 province (latitude: 37°50'_N, longitude: 4°51'_W, 91 m a.m.s.l.). The orchard, which
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3 belongs to the Andalusian Institute for Research and Formation in Agriculture and
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5 Fishery (IFAPA in Spanish), is located near the Guadalquivir River in a humid area
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7 where anthracnose is an endemic disease. Trees were planted in 1999 at four densities:
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10 3.5 m between rows and 1.5 m within rows (1904 trees/ha), 3.5 × 3.5 m (816 trees/ha),
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12 3.5 × 7.0 m (408 trees/ha), or 7.0 × 7.0 m (204 trees/ha) in a north–south orientation.
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14 The trees were planted in a complete block design, with two olive rows of each planting
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16 density per block and four blocks in total. In November 2003, trees were harvested, and
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18 500 fruit from each row (4000 fruit per planting density) were arbitrarily selected and
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20 evaluated for symptoms of anthracnose. The effect of the height of fruit in the olive
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22 canopy was evaluated by harvesting 500 fruit at 1.5 m height and 500 fruit at 3.0 m
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24 height from each row of the highest planting density (1904 trees/ha). In both cases, all
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26 fruit were evaluated for anthracnose symptoms. Non-symptomatic fruit were incubated
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28 in a humid chamber (100% HR) at 20°C in the dark to evaluate the incidence of latent
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30 infection. The experiment was repeated (trial 2) in November of 2004.
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34 **Data analyses.** All trials were conducted two or three times, and the
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36 homogeneity of variances between trials was tested using Bartlett's test of homogeneity.
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38 Because variances were homogeneous, data from repetitions of the same trial were
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40 combined for statistical analyses. Data for disease incidence and severity were subjected
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42 to one- or two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) according to the experiment, and
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44 when ANOVAs were significant, means were compared with Fisher's protected least
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46 significant difference (LSD) at $P = 0.05$. The cultivars were studied independently
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48 because they differ in susceptibility to anthracnose (18). Various linear and nonlinear
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50 regression models were evaluated for describing the relationship between disease
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52 severity and temperature. The Analytis Beta model (9) was selected because it provided
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a good fit for all combinations of isolates and cultivars and because it has been used with other olive pathogens (32). The Analytis Beta model uses the following equation:

$$Y = k \times t^a \times (1 - t)^b$$

in which Y = standardized disease severity ($Y = S/S_{max}$), t = standardized temperature [$t = (T - T_{min}) / (T_{max} - T_{min})$], and k , a , and b are unknown parameters. T_{min} and T_{max} were the minimum and maximum temperatures for infection. Linear regression was applied to test the relationship between data estimated by nonlinear regression and observed data. The best regression model was chosen from many combinations of terms based on the significance of the estimated parameters ($P \leq 0.05$), Mallows' C_p statistic, Akaike's information criterion modified for small data sets, the coefficient of determination (R^2), R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom (R_a^2), and the pattern of residuals over predicted and independent variables. Parabolic curves ($Y = a + bX + cX^2$) were fitted to the values MLP (day) versus temperature for each combination of isolate and temperature, and the optimum temperatures were calculated in the fitted equations. Linear regression analysis was used to evaluate the relationship between wetness duration and the percentage of affected fruit (with or without logarithmic transformation). When the fruit from non-inoculated control plants from a commercial nursery showed latent infection, the mean value of infections among these controls was subtracted from the mean value on fruit from inoculated olive plants.

The results from the wetness duration and temperature trials were used to develop an infection model according to Magarey *et al.* (15). The model of Magarey *et al.* (15) was used because we could not simultaneously control temperature and wetness with potted plants; the potted plants used in experiment 2 were too large for conventional temperature-controlled growth chambers.

According to the infection model of Magarey *et al.* (15), the wetness duration requirement ($W_{(T)}$) for the critical disease threshold at temperature T was calculated as:

$$W_{(T)} = \frac{W_{min}}{f_{(T)}} \leq W_{max}$$

where $W_{(T)}$ = wetness duration requirement (in hours) for the critical disease threshold at temperature T , W_{min} = the minimum value of the wetness duration requirement for the critical disease threshold at any temperature, and $f_{(T)}$ = temperature response function (35). The temperature model uses a pathogen's cardinal temperatures to estimate the shape parameter and the temperature response:

$$f_{(T)} = \left(\frac{T_{max} - T}{T_{max} - T_{opt}} \right) \left(\frac{T - T_{min}}{T_{opt} - T_{min}} \right)^{(T_{opt} - T_{min}) / (T_{max} - T_{opt})}$$

where T = mean temperature (°C) during the wetness period, T_{min} = minimum temperature for infection, T_{max} = maximum temperature for infection, and T_{opt} = optimum temperature for infection. Two critical disease thresholds of 10 and 20% of affected fruit were selected because a relatively low incidence of diseased fruit adversely affects the quality of olive oil (6). The model prediction was calculated in MS Excel (Microsoft, Redmond, WA). Data were analyzed using SPSS Software (version 14.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL).

RESULTS

Effect of temperature on infection (experiment 1). *Trial 1.* Both *C. acutatum* isolates (Col-09 and Col-30) caused anthracnose symptoms on black olive fruit of cv. Hojiblanca at temperatures ranging from 10 to 30°C. The first symptoms on the fruit were observed 4 days after inoculation. Inoculated fruit incubated at <25°C generally developed soapy rot symptoms with abundant production of conidia in a gelatinous matrix. When the fruit were incubated at 25 or 30°C, however, the main symptom was fruit mummification. None of the non-inoculated fruit developed anthracnose

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4 symptoms. The effect of isolate and the interaction between isolate and temperature on
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6 disease severity were highly significant ($P < 0.0001$). Isolate Col-09 was significantly
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8 ($P = 0.0275$) more virulent than Col-30 at 30°C (Fig. 1A). The fitted Analytis Beta
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10 models (Table 1) for each isolate are illustrated in Figure 1. All estimated parameters
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12 were significant ($P < 0.0001$); R^2 and R_a^2 were > 0.85 ; and the standardized residuals
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14 were randomly distributed over predicted Y and t for each isolate. There were significant
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16 ($P < 0.0215$) differences between the predicted temperatures of maximum disease
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18 severities, which were 24.1 and 20.2°C for isolates Col-09 and Col-30, respectively.

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21 *Trial 2.* Green-yellow olive fruit were susceptible to *C. acutatum* isolate Col-104
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23 and *C. simmondsii* isolate Col-116. The first anthracnose symptoms were observed on
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25 fruit of cvs. Picual and Hojiblanca inoculated with *C. acutatum* at 14 and 21 days after
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27 inoculation, respectively. Both fungal species infected fruit from 10 to 25°C, although
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29 some fruit of cv. Picual that were inoculated with *C. acutatum* developed disease
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31 symptoms at 5°C. Conversely, only *C. simmondsii* isolate Col-116 caused symptoms on
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33 some fruit of both cultivars at 30°C. For both cultivars, the effect of species,
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35 temperature, and the interaction between species and temperature on disease severity
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37 were highly significant ($P < 0.001$). *C. acutatum* isolate Col-104 was significantly ($P <$
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39 0.05) more virulent than *C. simmondsii* isolate Col-116 at 10, 15, and 20°C on both
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41 olive cultivars. The Analytis Beta model well described the relationship between
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43 temperature and disease severity (Fig. 2). For all species–cultivar combinations, P was
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45 < 0.0001 , R^2 and R_a^2 were > 0.90 , and the standardized residuals were randomly
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47 distributed over predicted Y and t . The predicted temperature of maximum disease
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49 severity was 17.0 to 20.4°C depending on the combination species and cultivar (Table
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51 1). When the latent period was studied, *C. simmondsii* isolate Col-116 was less affected
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53 by temperature than *C. acutatum* isolate Col-104 (Fig. 3). At the optimum temperature,
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3 the MLP ranged from 19.5 days (for the combination of resistant cv. Picual and *C.*
4 *simmondsii* isolate Col-116) to 26.1 days (for the combination of susceptible cv.
5 Hojiblanca and *C. acutatum* isolate Col-104). When fruit inoculated with *C. acutatum*
6 isolate Col-104 were incubated at 10 or 30°C, the MLP increased from 5 to 10 days.
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11 *Trial 3.* When the inoculated fruit were pre-incubated at 20°C for 24 h, the results
12 were similar to those in trial 2, although both isolates caused weak infection on the fruit
13 of cv. Hojiblanca at 35°C. *C. acutatum* isolate Col-104 was more virulent on olive fruit
14 than *C. simmondsii* isolate Col-116 at low temperatures (< 20°C) (*data not shown*).
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21 **Effect of wetness duration on infection (experiment 2).** *Trial 1.* Typical
22 anthracnose symptoms were observed at 8 weeks after inoculation, which coincided
23 with the onset of fruit ripening and change in fruit color from green to green-yellow. In
24 general, the symptoms progressed until the entire surface of all fruit was covered with
25 the mycelia and pycnidia of the pathogen. None of the non-inoculated plants developed
26 anthracnose symptoms. The pathogen caused fruit rot at all incubation periods including
27 the 0-h treatment. Wetness period significantly ($P < 0.0001$) affected disease severity.
28 There were three homogeneous groups according to disease severity. Wetness periods
29 of 0 to 24 h resulted in an average disease severity of $\approx 22\%$. A 48-h wetness period,
30 however, resulted in a disease severity of 58.4%. The plants that were subjected to a 48-
31 h dry period after inoculation and were subsequently placed at 100% RH for 48 h had a
32 disease severity of 43.5%. In the 48-h and 48/48-h treatments, a second set of symptoms
33 developed that began as a drying of leaves and evolved into dieback of shoots and
34 branches.
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52 When olive plants of cv. Arbequina were inoculated in trial 2, some fruit showed
53 visible symptoms of anthracnose in the plant canopy 1 month after inoculation, although
54 most fruit showed anthracnose symptoms when they were treated with Paraquat and
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3 incubated in humid chambers. It is worth noting that $\approx 2.5\%$ of the fruit that came from
4 non-inoculated control plants growing in commercial nurseries showed latent infection
5 of the pathogen. The percentage of affected fruit increased linearly with increasing
6 wetness duration from 0 to 48 h (Fig. 4A). The lowest wetness duration that resulted in
7 disease development was the 0-h treatment with an incidence of $\approx 5\%$. However, when
8 the wetness duration was 48 h, the disease incidence was $\approx 50\%$. In this case, the plants
9 did not show dieback of the shoots and branches. In the third wetness-duration trial,
10 olive shoots of cv. Arbequina were used in order to avoid natural latent infection by the
11 pathogen. In this case, the initial symptoms of anthracnose were observed 1 week after
12 inoculation. The percentage of affected fruit increased log-linearly with increasing
13 wetness duration between 0 and 48 h (Fig. 4A).
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28 The results of the temperature and wetness experiment were used to develop an
29 infection model for *C. acutatum* in the Andalusian region, with T_{min} , T_{max} , and T_{opt}
30 of 10, 25, and 20.4°C, respectively. At the optimum temperature, the two thresholds of
31 10 and 20% of affected fruit corresponded to wetness duration periods of 2.6 and 12.2
32 h, respectively (Fig. 5).
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39 **Effect of planting density on incidence of affected fruit (experiment 3).** A
40 significant anthracnose epidemic developed in the research orchard in 2003, when trial
41 1 of experiment 3 was conducted. The percentage of affected fruit ranged from 12.2 to
42 95.2%. The effect of planting density on percentages of symptomatic fruit and latent
43 infections was highly significant ($P < 0.0001$), whereas it had no influence ($P = 0.234$)
44 on total infection, i.e., numbers of affected fruit plus fruit with latent infections (Fig. 6).
45 The percentage of affected fruit was higher ($P < 0.0001$) in the highest density planting
46 (1904 trees/ha) than with the other three planting densities, among which the percentage
47 did not differ (Fig. 6A). Consistent with this, the percentage of fruit with latent
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3 infections was significantly ($P < 0.0001$) lower with the highest density planting than
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5 with the other three planting densities (Fig. 6B). The percentages of affected fruit and
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7 latent infections were significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by the height of fruit in the olive
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9 canopy in the densest planting; the percentages were higher for fruit collected from the
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11 lower canopy (1.5 m) than for fruit from the top (3 m) of the canopy (47.6% vs. 26.8%).
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13 In addition, fruit from the top of the canopy had more latent infections (53.7%) than
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15 those from the lower canopy (26.8%), although fruit height did not significantly affect
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17 total infection (Fig. 7).
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20 21 DISCUSSION

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23 In this study, temperature and wetness duration conditions that favored the
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25 development of olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum* spp. were defined using the
26
27 three main olive cultivars currently planted in Spain (2) and several *Colletotrichum*
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29 isolates that belong to the genetic groups A2 and A4. The latter groups represent the
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31 dominant isolates in Portugal and in the central Andalusian region of southern Spain,
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33 respectively (29; J. Moral and A. Trapero, *unpublished data*), and *C. acutatum* group-
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35 A2 was recently reclassified as the new species *C. simmondsii* (26). In all experiments,
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37 a reproducible method to inoculate olive plants and detached fruit with *Colletotrichum*
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39 was used (20). This method has been previously used to assess cultivar resistance (18),
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41 pathogenic characteristics of the fungus (22), and virulence groups in the interaction of
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43 cultivar and isolate (34).
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48 Some important factors that affect anthracnose disease of olive (fruit maturity,
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50 inoculum dose, and cultivar resistance) were not included in this study because they
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52 were previously investigated in the development of the method to inoculate detached
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54 fruits and olive plants with *Colletotrichum* species (18,20). The infection of olive fruit
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56 by *Colletotrichum* species in the current study was influenced by temperature and
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wetness duration, which also influences infection in other *Colletotrichum* pathosystems (8,12,33). When wetness was not a limiting factor, inoculation of detached fruit showed that infection occurred between 10 and 25°C. Infection was weak, however, at 5 and 30°C depending on fungal isolate, cultivar, and fruit ripeness. The Analytis Beta function was useful for describing the relationship between disease severity and temperature. According to this function, the optimum temperature for infection ranged from 17.0 to 24.1°C depending on isolate and fruit ripeness. This value is within the optimal range of 20 to 24°C for germination of conidia (10,23) and inoculum production from mummified olive fruit by *C. acutatum* isolates in Spain (19). Loprieno and Tenerini (13), in contrast, found an optimum temperature between 25 and 30°C for conidial germination of Italian isolates of the pathogen. Under field conditions, Kaul and Thakur (11) determined that the optimum temperature for olive leaf infection is between 17 and 22°C. These differences could be due to genetic variation within and among populations of *Colletotrichum* species that attack olive in different geographic regions. Molecular, physiological, and phenotypic analyses have revealed substantially diversity among olive isolates of *Colletotrichum* from Italy, Portugal, and Spain (1,22,23,29). In the present study, at suboptimal temperatures for infection, latent periods increased substantially. Others have reported similar results with artificially inoculated olive fruit (13). This may explain why, when temperatures drop in the field during December, fruit with latent infections do not express anthracnose symptoms for several weeks (19).

In our experiments, anthracnose infection and develop were similar for the resistant cv. Picual and the susceptible cv. Hojiblanca. The similar level of disease among these cultivars was probably due to the use of fruit that differed in ripeness; although the fruit color (green-yellow) indicated ripening stage 1 for both cultivars, the true ripening

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3 stage, based on the maturity of internal tissues (2), was probably higher for the more
4
5 resistant cv. Picual. This was suspected because many inoculated fruit of cv. Picual
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7 quickly changed to a violet color (ripening stage 3). Differences between internal and
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9 external fruit ripening stages have been previously reported for other olive cultivars
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11 (2,18).
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14 For many aerial pathogens, an infection submodel is critical for disease forecasting
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16 (14) because infection is usually limited by the duration of surface wetness or high
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18 humidity (15). When temperature was not a limiting factor, infections were detected at
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20 all wetness periods, including 0 h. Overall, disease severity increased with the wetness
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22 period from 0 to 48 h, although this relationship was less clear when potted plants with
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24 developing fruit were inoculated during September, perhaps because of the effect of
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26 ripening. This is in accordance with the observation that, although the pathogen infects
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28 the developing olive fruit, the infections remain latent until the onset of ripening when
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30 fruit color changes during the fall (21). When potted plants with green-yellow fruit at
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32 the onset of ripening were inoculated, the incidence of symptomatic fruit increased
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34 linearly with the wetness duration. Similar effects of wetness period on disease
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36 development have been described for other hosts affected by *C. acutatum* (8,33). It is
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38 interesting that, in our study, 2.5% of the fruit obtained from potted plants growing in a
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40 commercial nursery showed latent infections of the pathogen. Survival of
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42 *Colletotrichum* on asymptomatic olive fruit could have implications for long-distance
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44 dissemination of the pathogen on potted plants. To avoid the interaction of latent
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46 infections in our experiments, we initially inoculated detached olive fruit collected from
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48 healthy trees, but when fruit were incubated at low relative humidity (< 80%), they
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50 quickly dehydrated (J. Moral and A. Trapero, *unpublished data*). The inoculation of
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52 stem cuttings bearing fruit collected from healthy cv. Arbequina olive trees allowed us
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2
3 to study the effect of wetness duration on disease severity. As noted earlier, infections
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5 were detected with all wetness periods tested, even 0 h, although the infections with this
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7 wetness period were weak. The short time that elapsed from when the plants were
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9 inoculated until they were completely dry in the 0-h treatment may have been sufficient
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11 for conidia to germinate, produce appressoria, and infect the fruit. In previous studies,
12
13 conidial germination of *C. acutatum* isolates from olive was favored by an increase in
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15 the wetness duration, and about 20% of the conidia germinated and formed appressoria
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17 with a 3-h wetness period (10,23). This represents a very short “minimal wetness period
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19 for infection” among aerial fungal pathogens. For example, the minimal wetness period
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21 for infection of olive leaves by *Fusicladium oleagineum* is 12 h (32).
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26 Because the effects of wetness duration and temperature are interdependent, they
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28 should be considered together (8,9,32,33). Using the generated data on the wetness
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30 duration and temperature trials, we developed an infection model according to Margarey
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32 *et al.* (15) for the Andalusian region. The critical disease thresholds were defined as
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34 10% and 20% of affected fruit because olive oil from fruit with 16% of affected fruit
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36 loses the top quality classification (virgin extra) according to the European Community
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38 Regulations (6). This model was selected because it can use inputs based on
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40 independent temperature and wetness duration trials and because it successfully
41
42 described the relationship between temperature and wetness on disease infection on
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44 other *Colletotrichum* hosts (15,17,33). Unfortunately, the combined temperature-
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46 wetness duration experiment is complicated on olive due to the large size of the adult
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48 potted plants and the inability to use detached fruit. Using preliminary data, we have
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50 found that the model is useful for describing the infection process (J. Moral and A.
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52 Trapero, *unpublished data*) during the high risk months of October and November (19).
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In the last decade, olive growers have tended to increase the density of trees in olive plantations from 70–100 trees/ha to >2000 trees/ha (2,24). For many pathosystems, microclimatic changes resulting from higher plant densities usually improve the conditions for disease development (3,27). Increased plant density is likely to increase the duration of wetness on host tissues. Although the concept that growing plants in dense stands contributes to severe epidemics is an accepted axiom (3), it is supported by only limited experimental data. The current study is the first to report on how planting density affects development of olive anthracnose under field conditions. We observed that the percentage of affected fruit was highest in the densest plantings, although there was no difference among the planting densities on total fruit infection (symptomatic plus latent infections). This indicates that the epidemic progressed fastest in the densest plantings and that important anthracnose epidemics may develop in dense planting even with a moderately resistant cultivar like Arbequina (18). An increase in the incidence of olive leaf spot caused by *F. oleagineum* related to an increase in planting density has also been observed in olive orchards (30). Nevertheless, superhigh-density olive orchards can be successfully managed by increasing pruning intensity and by increasing the number of copper fungicide treatments (J. Moral and A. Trapero, *unpublished data*).

Finally, our results indicate that forecast models for olive anthracnose should take into account the dominant species of the pathogen, the resistance of the cultivars, and tree density.

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LITERATURE CITED

1. Agosteo, G. E., Magnano di San Lio, G., Cacciola, S. O., and Frisullo, S. 2002. Characterisation of the causal agent of olive anthracnose in southern Italy. *Acta Hortic.* 586:713-716.
2. Barranco, D., Fernández-Escobar, R., and Rallo, L. 2010. Olive growing. Junta de Andalucía / Mundi-Prensa / RIRDC, Australia.
3. Burdon, J. J., and Chilvers, G. A. 1982. Host density as a factor in plant disease ecology. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 20:143-166.
4. Cacciola, S. O., Pane, A., Agosteo, G. E., and Magnano di San Lio, G. 1996. Osservazioni sull' epidemiologia dell'anthracnosi dell'olivo in Calabria. *Inf. Fitopatol.* 6:27-32.
5. Campbell CL, Madden LV, 1990. Introduction to plant diseases epidemiology. John Willey & Sons. NY, USA.
6. Carvalho, M. T., Simões-Lopes, P., and Monteiro da Silva, M. J. 2004. Influence of different olive infection rates of *Colletotrichum acutatum* in some important olive oil chemical parameters. *Acta Hortic.* 791:57-59.
7. de Andrés, F. 1991. Enfermedades y plagas del Olivo. Riquelme y Vargas Ediciones S.L., Jaén, Spain.

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8. Diéguez-Uribeondo, J., Förster, H., and Adaskaveg, J. E. 2011. Effect of wetness duration and temperature on the development of anthracnose on selected almond tissues and comparison of cultivar susceptibility. *Phytopathology* 101:1013-1020.
9. Hau, B., and Kranz, J. 1990. Mathematics and statistics for analyses in epidemiology. Pages 15-22 in: *Epidemics of Plant Diseases*. J. Kranz, ed. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Germany.
10. Jurado-Bello, J. 2010. Efecto de la temperatura, tiempo de humectación y potencial osmótico en la infección de aceitunas, germinación de conidios y crecimiento micelial de *Colletotrichum* spp. agente causal de la Antracnosis del olivo. Trabajo Profesional Fin de Carrera, ETSIAM, Universidad de Córdoba, Córdoba, Spain.
11. Kaul, J. L., and Thakur, R. S. 1985. Incidence of olive anthracnose (*Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* Penz.) and its correlation with weather conditions. *J. Tree Sci.* 4:20-34.
12. Leandro, L. F. S., Gleason, M. L., Nutter, F. W., Jr., Wegulo, S. N., and Dixon, P. M. 2003. Influence of temperature and wetness duration on conidia and appressoria of *Colletotrichum acutatum* on symptomless strawberry leaves. *Phytopathology* 93:513-520.
13. Loprieno, N., and Tenerini, I. 1960. Indagini sul *Gloeosporium olivarum* Alm., agente della "lebbra" delle olive. *Phytopath. Z.* 39: 262-290.
14. Madden, L. V., and Ellis, M. A. 1988. How to develop plant disease forecasters. Pages 191-208 in: *Experimental Techniques in Plant Disease Epidemiology*. J. Rotem, ed. Springer-Verlag, New York.
15. Magarey, R. D., Sutton, T. B., and Thayer, C. L. 2005. A simple generic infection model for foliar fungal plant pathogens. *Phytopathology* 95:92-100.

J. Moral *et al.*,
Phytopathology

16. Martín, M. P., and García-Figueres, F. 1999. *Colletotrichum acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* cause anthracnose on olives. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 105:733-741.
17. Monroe, J. S., Santini, J. B., and Latin, R. 1997. A model defining the relationship between temperature and leaf wetness duration, and infection of watermelon by *Colletotrichum orbiculare*. *Plant Dis.* 81:739-742
18. Moral, J., and Trapero, A. 2009. Assessing the susceptibility of olive cultivars to anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Plant Dis.* 93:1028-1036
19. Moral, J., and Trapero, A. 2012. Mummified fruit as a source of inoculum and infection dynamics of olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Phytopathology* 102: (*in revision*).
20. Moral, J., Bouhmidi, K., and Trapero, A. 2008. Influence of fruit maturity, cultivar susceptibility, and inoculation method on infection of olive fruit by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Plant Dis.* 92:1421-1426.
21. Moral, J., Oliveira, R., and Trapero, A. 2009. Elucidation of the disease cycle of olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Phytopathology* 99:548-556.
22. Moral, J., Oliveira, R., Tello, J.C., Trapero, A. 2007. Caracterización fisiológica y patogénica de aislados de *Colletotrichum* spp. causantes de la Antracnosis del olivo. *Bol. San. Veg. Plagas* 33:219-234.
23. Oliveira, R., Moral, J., Bouhmidi, K., and Trapero, A. 2005. Caracterización morfológica y cultural de aislados de *Colletotrichum* spp. causantes de la Antracnosis del olivo. *Bol. San. Veg. Plagas* 31:531-548.
24. Pastor, M., Fereres, E., Vega, V., and Hidalgo, J. C. 2006. Viabilidad económica de plantaciones superintensivas en Andalucía. *Vida Rural* 238:60-66.

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25. Rallo, L., Barranco, D., Caballero, J. M., del Río, C., Martín, A., Tous, J., and Trujillo, I., eds. 2005. *Varietades de Olivo en España*. Junta de Andalucía, M.A.P.A. & Mundi- Prensa, Madrid, Spain.
26. Shivas, R.G., and Tan, Y.P. 2009. A taxonomic re-assessment of *Colletotrichum acutatum*, introducing *C. fioriniae* comb. et stat. nov. and *C. simmondsii* sp. nov. *Fungal Diversity* 39: 111-122.
27. Strandberg, J. O., and White, J. M. 1978. *Cercospora apii* damage of celery: effects of plant spacing and growth on raised beds. *Phytopathology* 68:223-226.
28. Talhinhos, P., Mota-Capitão, C., Martins, S., Ramos, A. P., Neves-Martins, J., Guerra-Guimarães, L., Várzea, V., Silva, M. C., Sreenivasaprasad, S., Oliveira, H. 2011. Epidemiology, histopathology and aetiology of olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* in Portugal. *Plant Pathology* 60:483-495.
29. Talhinhos, P., Sreenivasaprasad, S., Neves-Martins, J., and Oliveira, H. 2005. Molecular and phenotypic analyses reveal association of diverse *Colletotrichum acutatum* groups and a low level of *C. gloeosporioides* with olive anthracnose. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 71:2987-2998.
30. Trapero, A. 2007. Densidad de plantación y enfermedades del olivar. *Mercacei* 51:210-213.
31. Trapero, A., and Blanco, M. A. 2010. Diseases. Pages 521-578 in: *Olive growing*. D. Barranco, R. Fernández-Escobar, and L. Rallo, eds. Junta de Andalucía / Mundi-Prensa / RIRDC / AOA, Pendle Hill, NSW, Australia.
32. Viruega, J. R., Roca, L. F., Moral, J., and Trapero, A. 2011. Factors affecting infection and disease development on olive leaves inoculated with *Fusicladium oleagineum*. *Plant Dis.* 95:1139-1146.

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33. Wilson, L. L., Madden, L. V., and Ellis, M. A. 1990. Influence of temperature and wetness duration on infection of immature and mature strawberry fruit by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Phytopathology* 80:111-116.
34. Xaviér, C. J. 2009. Resistencia y grupos de virulencia en la Antracnosis del olivo causada por *Colletotrichum* spp. Master's Thesis, ETSIAM, Universidad de Córdoba, Córdoba, Spain.
35. Yin, X., Kropff, M. J., McLaren, G., and Visperas, R. M. 1995. A nonlinear model for crop development as a function of temperature. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 77:1-16.

TABLE 1. Effect of temperature on disease severity on olive fruit inoculated with *Colletotrichum* species (experiment 1)

Isolate	Species	Cultivar	Fruit ripening ^{y,z} [color class (0-4)]	Analytis Beta model parameters ^x				Topt (°C)
				<i>K</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>R</i> ²	
Col-09	<i>C. acutatum</i>	Hojiblanca	Black (4)	2.2653	0.9081	0.7065	0.9623	24.1
Col-30	<i>C. acutatum</i>	Hojiblanca	Black (4)	8.1291	1.3543	1.9884	0.8911	20.2
Col-104	<i>C. acutatum</i>	Hojiblanca	Green-yellow (1)	5.2927	1.3036	1.2405	0.9920	20.4
Col-104	<i>C. acutatum</i>	Picual	Green-yellow (1)	3.4459	0.8013	1.2011	0.9286	17.0
Col-116	<i>C. simmondsii</i>	Hojiblanca	Green-yellow (1)	47.839	3.0236	3.3538	0.9851	19.2
Col-116	<i>C. simmondsii</i>	Picual	Green-yellow (1)	7.5313	1.5718	2.1508	0.9372	17.7

^xDisease severity (*Y*) and temperature (*t*) data were adjusted to a nonlinear Analytis Beta model $Y = k \times t^a \times (1 - t)^b$ (Hau and Kranz, 1990).

^yDetached fruit were inoculated with a conidial suspension and incubated at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, and 35°C in humid chambers.

^zRipening scale from green (0) to black (4) according to Rallo *et al.*, 2005.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Effect of temperature on the relative area under the disease progress curve (RAUDPC) for black olive fruit of cv. Hojiblanca inoculated with two isolates of *Colletotrichum acutatum* (experiment 1). Bars and points represent the average of 150 fruit. The curves represent the Analytis Beta functions, $Y = k \times t^a \times (1 - t)^b$, relating the RAUDPC to temperature. The equations fit the observed data with $R^2 > 0.85$.

Figure 2. Effect of temperature on disease severity [symptoms development rate (day⁻¹)] on green-yellow olive fruit of cvs. Hojiblanca and Picual inoculated with *Colletotrichum acutatum* (Col-104) and *C. simmondsii* (Col-116). Bars and points represent the average of 150 fruit (experiment 1). The curves represent the Analytis Beta functions, $Y = k \times t^a \times (1 - t)^b$, relating disease severity to temperature. The equations fit the observed data with R^2 and $R_a^2 > 0.90$.

Figure 3. Effect of temperature on mean latent period (days) on green-yellow olive fruit of cvs. Hojiblanca and Picual inoculated with *Colletotrichum acutatum* (Col-104) and *C. simmondsii* (Col-116) (experiment 1). Points represent the average of 150 fruit. The curves represent the parabolic functions, $Y = a + bt^2 + ct^3$, relating the mean latent period to temperature. The equations fit the observed data with $R^2 > 0.85$.

Figure 4. Regression of wetness duration (h) on the incidence (%) of olive anthracnose on fruit caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum* (experiment 2). Percentage of symptomatic fruit on inoculated plants of cv. Arbequina (A) and on inoculated stem cuttings of cv. Arbequina (B). Points represent the average of 10 potted olive plants (A) or stem cuttings (B). Bars represent the standard error of each mean.

Figure 5. Relative risk of infection of olive fruit by *Colletotrichum acutatum* based on wetness period (W) and temperature (T) as predicted by an infection model based on

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Magarey et al. (15). The upper and lower lines represent the contour plots for 10% and 20% of disease incidence.

Figure 6. Effect of olive tree density on **A**, fruit with olive anthracnose symptoms (%), **B**, fruit with olive anthracnose latent infection (%), and **C**, total infection (%), based on fruit with symptoms plus fruit with latent infection). Bars represent the average of 4,000 fruit at each tree density. For each tree density, mean values with the same letter are not significantly different according to Fisher's protected least significant difference test at $P = 0.05$.

Figure 7. Effect of fruit height (m) in the olive tree canopy on incidence of symptomatic fruit and fruit with latent infection by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. Bars represent the average of 2,000 fruit at each plant height. For each plant height, mean values of affected fruit (lower case letters) or fruit with latent infection (upper case letters) with the same letter are not significantly different according to Fisher's protected least significant difference test at $P = 0.05$. Total fruit infection (based on fruit with symptoms plus fruit with latent infections, i.e., the total height of the two bars) was not significantly affected ($P = 0.460$) by fruit height.

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Figure 5

Review

Figure 6

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Figure 7

Peer Review

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